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ORIENTATION AND STABILIZATION OF MARINE UNMANNED SYSTEMS WITH HWT-905 IMU: AN EXPERIMENTAL STM32-BASED APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the integration and effectiveness of the HWT-905 digital inclinometer based on the STM32 microcontroller for control systems of marine unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). The key role of inclinometers in ensuring accurate orientation, stabilization and navigation of UAVs in a dynamic marine environment, where traditional positioning methods are limited, is substantiated.

The principle of operation of inclinometers based on MEMS accelerometers, formulas for calculating pitch and roll angles, as well as the limitations of static measurements in dynamic conditions are described. Attention is paid to the HWT-905 sensor as an integrated inertial measurement unit (IMU) that combines an accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer with an integrated data processing system, providing high accuracy and low latency.

A comparative analysis of the HWT-905 with other IMU sensors (MPU-9250, BNO055, LSM9DS1) is carried out in terms of such parameters as interface, embedded computing, dimensions, software support, power consumption, and noise stability. The architecture is presented software implementation on STM32 and an example of integrating HWT-905 data into the logic of the MBA autopilot.

Experimental tests on a prototype of the UAV showed significant advantages of the HWT-905 in orientation accuracy, stabilization time, resistance to false positives, as well as the efficiency of using microcontroller resources compared to alternative solutions. It is concluded that the HWT-905 based on STM32 is a rational solution for increasing the autonomy and reliability of marine unmanned systems. Promising directions for further research are outlined, including the use of machine learning, integration with other sensors (RTK-GNSS, hydroacoustic systems, video streams) and the development of multi-sensor fusion.

Keywords: inclinometer, marine unmanned aerial vehicles, IMU, HWT-905, navigation, stabilization, orientation, MEMS, accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer, autopilot, sensor fusion, autonomous systems.

Introduction. Inclinometer, a sensor used to measure the angle of inclination, height or depression of an object, relative to the direction of gravity. Such a sensor works on the basis of creating an artificial horizon, measuring the angular inclination relative to this reference point.

Inclinometers are widely used in various industries. Inclinometers play a special role in modern maritime practice. In particular, they play vital roles in marine unmanned systems. They operate in a dynamic and complex maritime environment, where obtaining accurate information about the vessel's position is critical not only for navigation, mission execution and data collection, but also for the safety of navigation.

1. The main objectives of using inclinometers in marine unmanned systems are as follows:

- measuring position and orientation. Inclinometers measure pitch (forward-backward tilt) and roll

(side-to-side tilt) of unmanned aerial vehicles. Also used in automatic systems to calm the ship from rolling;

- navigation and control for autonomous and unmanned underwater and surface vehicles - inclinometer data is integrated with other sensors (such as gyroscopes, accelerometers, magnetometers, Doppler velocity logs, and GPS) to provide reliable navigation solutions, especially in underwater environments or areas where GPS is unavailable;

- stabilization - marine unmanned systems carry various useful loads such as sonar, cameras, lidars and other scientific instruments for data collection. Inclinometers ensure the stabilization of these platforms with high accuracy of the collected data and the absence of distortions caused by the movement of the platforms;

- real-time monitoring and data accuracy - inclinometers, in particular dynamic ones, containing gyroscopes together with accelerometers, can measure tilt even during movement and vibrations.

The problems of using inclinometers are as follows. 1. External accelerations and oscillations (rapid accelerated movements, vibrations or impacts can introduce errors into the slope measurement, as inclinometers rely on gravity as a reference).

2. Errors in assembly of the structure, damage or deformation housing, probe positioning errors; checksum calculation errors caused by imperfections in the electrical axis alignment of the internal sensor.

3. System errors:

- systematic errors (constant deviation of readings, sensitivity drift and the combined effect of casing inclination and sensor axis alignment offset;

- lack of complete information, which requires additional sensors;

- the difficulty of measuring small slopes.

The constant development of inclinometer technologies increases the reliability and accuracy of measurements. That is why the study of modern digital inclinometers for orientation and stabilization of marine unmanned aerial vehicles, the development of their software, and comparison with known solutions are relevant practical scientific tasks.

Problem statement. In modern conditions for the development of autonomous In marine unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), significant attention is paid to stabilization, orientation, and navigation. One of the most effective means of solving this problem is the use of inertial measurement systems (IMUs), which include accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers. The integration of the IMU into the IBA control architecture allows for system autonomy in the absence of external sources of navigation information, such as GPS.

Analysis of recent research and publications. In [1], practical use and reliability assessment of an inclinometer in measuring and controlling balance are presented. In [2], research and engineering application of inclinometry technologies based on distributed fiberoptic sensing are conducted.

A new wireless low-cost inclinometer, created by combining measurements from multiple MEMS gyroscopes and accelerometers, is described in [3]. In [3], an inclinometer called LARA (Low-cost Adaptive Reliable Angle Measurer) is presented, which measures inclination by combining five gyroscopes and five accelerometers. Improving the accuracy of low-cost inclinometers using artificial intelligence is described in [4]. A distributed fiberoptic inclinometer with a cloud-based monitoring system is presented in [5]. The technical documentation [5] describes a modern digital position sensor-inclinometer series HWT905, but almost no comparisons and software for it are given.

In works [7-9], a high-performance MEMS IMU for low-cost navigation applications is described, a control architecture for robotic vehicles with inertial navigation is built, and a method for adaptive orientation estimation for marine navigation using a low-cost IMU and an extended filter is presented. Kalman.

The design of a marine unmanned vehicle based on the embedded STM32 and its architecture for real-time control of marine unmanned systems are given in [10, 11]. The general principles of inertial platform-free navigation, nonlinear complementary filters on a special orthogonal group, and documentation on the Robot Operating System (ROS) are given in [12-14].

Based on the above analysis, we can conclude that one of the sensors that can be used in the IBA is the HWT-905. This is a digital three-axis IMU module that provides output data of acceleration, angular velocity, tilt angle (orientation) and magnetic field in a convenient format. The device has a built-in parameter calculation system, which allows you to obtain already processed values without the need to implement complex filters on the controller side. Thanks to the simple UART interface, the sensor is easily integrated with popular STM32-based platforms. However, the manufacturer [9] of these devices does not provide practical and theoretical features of using IMU sensors to increase the autonomy and navigation accuracy of marine unmanned aerial vehicles in conditions of limited external orientation.

The article is a justification for the possibilities of sensor integration HWT-905 in the MBA management system, developed based on a microcontroller STM32.

Presentation of the main material. Inclinometers, or tilt sensors, measure the angle of inclination of an object relative to the Earth's gravitational field. Most modern inclinometers, especially in small unmanned aerial vehicles, are based on microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) with accelerometers. Micro-electromechanical systems (MEMS), or English: MEMS (Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems), is a technology for creating very small devices (from microns to several millimeters) that combine electrical and mechanical components at a microscopic level. These devices are manufactured using technologies similar to those used to produce integrated circuits, which allows the integration of micromechanical elements, sensors, actuators and electronics on a single semiconductor crystal.

The basic principle of operation of an inclinometer is to measure the components of the gravitational force acting on a sensor mass along different axes. When the inclinometer is tilted, the gravity vector is projected onto the sensor axis differently, which allows the angle of inclination to be calculated.

Calculating the tilt angle using a single-axis accelerometer is quite simple. Consider an accelerometer that measures acceleration a_{cx} along one axis (for example, X). If it is inclined, then the angle of inclination θ relative to the horizontal plane is calculated by the formula:

$$\theta = \arcsin(a_{cx}/g) \quad (1)$$

where a_{cx} - measured acceleration along the X axis, m/s^2 , g is the acceleration of gravity ($9.81 m/s^2$ or $1 g$). This formula applies if the X-axis is the sensitive axis and the tilt occurs in the plane containing this axis and the gravity vector.

Calculating roll and pitch angles using a three-axis accelerometer is a little more complicated.

For a more complete orientation (roll and pitch) use triaxial accelerometers that measure acceleration along the X, Y, and Z axes (a_{ccX} , a_{ccY} , a_{ccZ}).

These formulas assume static or quasi-static conditions, i.e. the absence of significant accelerations other than gravity. Pitch angle (Pitch, φ) is the angle of rotation around the Y axis:

$$\varphi = \arctan2(a_{ccX}, \sqrt{a_{ccY}^2 + a_{ccZ}^2}). \quad (2)$$

Roll angle (Roll, θ) is the angle of rotation around the X axis:

$$\theta = \arctan2(a_{ccY}, \sqrt{a_{ccX}^2 + a_{ccZ}^2}) \quad (3)$$

Where $\arctan2(y, x)$ is a two-argument arctangent function that returns an angle in the range $-\pi$ to π (-180° to 180°), taking into account the quadrant. This is important for correctly determining the sign of the angle (direction of the vector).

Acceleration a_{ccX} , a_{ccY} and a_{ccZ} – measured accelerometer values along the corresponding axes in units of gravity.

When analyzing data from inclinometers, it is often important to know not the absolute angle, but its change from the initial value (Change in Inclination):

$$\Delta\theta = G \cdot (R_1 - R_0) \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta\theta$ - change of inclination angle, G - conversion factor (Gauge Factor), specific to the sensor, R_1 - current sensor reading, R_0 - initial (zero) sensor reading.

All of these formulas are based on the assumption that the only significant acceleration acting on the sensor in a static state is gravity. These formulas are only accurate when the inclinometer is at rest or moving at very low linear or angular velocities with no significant accelerations (other than gravity). If the object is subjected to significant dynamic accelerations (such as during sudden movements of a ship), the accelerometer will measure the sum of gravity and these dynamic accelerations, which will result in inaccurate angle measurements.

Inclinometers (based on accelerometers) cannot directly measure yaw angle (Yaw) - rotation around a vertical axis. To measure yaw, additional sensors are required, such as magnetometers (compass) or gyroscopes (as part of inertial measurement units - IMUs).

The accuracy of inclinometers is affected by bias, scale factor, nonlinearity, hysteresis, and temperature drift. These errors are corrected through calibration.

That is why it is better to carry out all calculations using microprocessor technology.

Consider the HWT-905 sensor - an inertial measurement unit (IMU), an heading and heading system (AHRS). It is designed to accurately measure and output data on acceleration, angular velocity (gyro), orientation angle (pitch/roll/yaw) and magnetic field along three axes (X, Y, Z). Orientation (angle) determination is a key function of the HWT-905. It determines the inclination angles (pitch, roll) with an accuracy of up to 0.05° along the X and Y axes, as well as the heading angle (roll along the Z axis) with an accuracy of up to 1° (after magnetic calibration and in the absence of magnetic interference). This is achieved thanks to the built-in high-precision gyroscopes, accelerometers and magnetometers, as well as the use of data filtering algorithms. The sensor also allows measuring acceleration along three axes; measuring angular velocity using data from a gyroscope, allows you to determine the speed of rotation of the device around three axes; magnetic field measurement using a built-in magnetometer - measures the strength of the magnetic field, which is critically important for determining absolute heading (direction to north).

The HWT-905 sensor belongs to the class of integrated inertial measurement devices (IMU), combines a three-axis accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer. The device provides data on acceleration (m/s^2), angular velocities (deg/s), orientation (Roll, Pitch, Yaw), temperature ($^\circ C$), magnetic field vector (in conventional units). The main advantage of the HWT-905 is the preprocessing of data at the chip level.

Data transfer is carried out via the UART interface at a standard speed of 9600 b or 115200 b. For efficient reading of streaming data, a UART interrupt is used for each byte.

Table 1 provides a brief expert comparison of the HWT-905 with other popular IMU sensors for use in MBA (in points, where 10 is the maximum, 0 is the minimum).

Table 1

Comparison of IMU sensors

Paramete	Sensor type			
	HWT-905	MPU-9250	BNO055	LSM9DS1
Interface	UART	I2C/SPI	I2C/UART	I2C/SPI
Built-in calculation	8-9	0	8-9	0
Dimensions	8	9-10	4	7-8
Software support	9-10	9-10	8-10	5-9
Consumption energy	7	9	5	8-10
Stability in noise	9-10	7-9	8-10	5-7

The integration of the HWT-905 sensor into the control system of a marine unmanned aerial vehicle is implemented according to the modular structure of the firmware on STM32. The main software blocks: hwt905.c/h - driver for processing incoming UART data; sensor_manager.c/h - aggregation of data from various sensors, such as GPS, echo sounder, compass,

IMU, etc.; autopilot.c/h - decision-making based on orientation, navigation, path; main.c - system initialization, start of the polling cycle.

Sensor information of direction (autopilot) is used in control algorithms of stabilization and navigation. Thus, course stabilization is implemented using the P-regulator:

```

c
float course_error = normalize_angle(target_yaw - hwt905.angle.yaw);
float rudder_output = course_error * COURSE_KP;
motor_control_set_rudder(rudder_output);
}
    
```

The normalization function used here is `normalize_angle()` to the range $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$ to avoid incorrect rotation through 0° . As the HWT-905 continuously transmits data, the system enters UART interrupt wait mode. This allows the main polling cycle frequency to be reduced and avoids active "idle" processing.

The HWT-905 sensor provides orientation data in terms of Euler angles (roll, pitch, yaw), which are critical for closed-loop course stabilization, hull tilt, and wave disturbance compensation. The sensor's built-in filters provide smoothed, ready-to-use values without the need for computationally complex algorithms such as Kalman or Madgwick.

The HWT-905 sensor works simultaneously with the following modules: GPS (positioning); echo

sounder (depth measurement); compass (backup orientation).

Integration is carried out through `sensor_manager`, which aggregates data streams into a common `navigation_state_t` structure, which simplifies access to sensor information for the navigation module:

```

c
typedef struct {
float latitude, longitude;
float depth;
float heading; // from HWT-905
float yaw_compass; // from magnetometer
navigation_state_t;
}
    
```

Each yaw measurement is checked for plausibility based on previous values. In the autopilot subroutine, the decision-making module (`decision_maker`) uses orientation data to determine the stability of the aircraft, to adjust the route in case of disturbances, and to avoid the aircraft from turning over during extreme tilt.

Table 2

Expert assessments of alternative implementations of inclinometers (for 10 point scale)

Parameter	Solution on HWT-905	Alternative (MPU9250 + compass)
Filtration	10	4-8
Synchronization complexity	8-10	2-7
Delay	<5 мс	~20–50 мс
Power consumption (STM32)	8-10	5-8
Code volume	8-10	3-5
Reliability in noise	7-10	3-5

The signal delay in the HWT-905 is less than 5 ms, and in the MPU9250 with a compass - up to 50 ms. It can be concluded that the HWT-905 system acts as a more integrated and reliable solution, which reduces the overall complexity of the system. Testing of the stabilization system with the HWT-905 sensor was carried out on a prototype of the MBA in inland waters (calm

water, wind up to 4 m/s) and on an open water body (waves up to 0.5 m). System parameters: architecture: STM32F407, RTOS (FreeRTOS); HWT-905 sensors (IMU), GPS Neo-7M, echo sounder; IMU update frequency 50 Hz; actuator control frequency 20 Hz.

The results of the experiments are given in Table 3.

Table 3

Results of experimental tests of inclinometers

Метрика	HWT-905 (integrated)	Alternative (MPU9250 + compass)
T1 (average orientation error)	±1.4°	±4.1°
T2(stabilization time)	1,1 с	2,9 с
T3 (number of false positives)	0 за 1 год	3 за 1 год
T4 (RAM/Flash)	12 кБ / 28 кБ	22 кБ / 44 кБ
Kernel loading (average)	28 %	47 %
IMU processing costs	6 %	21 %
Stabilization cycle time	1,3 мс	3,5 мс

It should be noted that the HWT-905 provides significantly lower error and stabilization time. Built-in filtering makes the system more resistant to noise compared to other types of data processing from individual sensors.

The use of HWT-905 in the IBA allows you to shorten the development cycle, reduce energy consumption, ensure stable orientation even on a simple STM32, adapt UAV practices to maritime platforms without excessive complexity. Thus, the architecture

with HWT-905 based on STM32 is an evolutionary response to the needs of maritime unmanned systems. It transfers and uses the best practices of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), but taking into account the specifics of the maritime environment.

Although the HWT-905 provides processed data, there is potential to extend its capabilities through additional processing on the STM32 microcontroller. In particular, this is the implementation of a floating-average filter for noise smoothing. For example, as follows:

```

c
# define FILTER_WINDOW 5float
yaw_buffer[FILTER_WINDOW];
uint8_t yaw_index = 0;
float smooth_yaw(float new_yaw) {
    yaw_buffer[yaw_index] = new_yaw;
    yaw_index = (yaw_index + 1) %
FILTER_WINDOW;
    float sum = 0;
    for (int i = 0; i < FILTER_WINDOW; i++) {
        sum += yaw_buffer[i];
    }
    return sum / FILTER_WINDOW;
}

```

For more precise control, it is possible to switch to using quaternions or rotation matrices, which is especially important when maneuvering in 3D mode. In the future, it is possible to supplement with machine learning algorithms that will detect sensor degradation based on defined trends.

The architecture developed by the authors is scalable to work with multiple IMUs (for example, redundant or for their combination), as well as for integration with GNSS/RTK, echo sounders, and cameras.

One of the promising directions is the combination of IMU data with video streams: to estimate the position of the device relative to coastal objects, to correct orientation drifts, to work in environments without GPS. In this case, the HWT-905 acts as a reference source of orientation, complementing visual SLAM algorithms.

Conclusions

A justification of the possibilities of integrating HWT-905 sensors into the IBA control system has been carried out, developed based on a microcontroller STM32. The features of the software implementation are presented, and the advantages and disadvantages of the proposed solution in comparison with other sensors are analyzed.

The next steps of the research include: and integration with RTK-GNSS and hydroacoustic systems for positioning, development of adaptive filtering algorithms with machine learning to recognize sensor failures, integration into ROS (Robot Operating System) for use in complex missions with Multi-sensor Fusion to combine data obtained from several different sensors and obtain more accurate, complete and reliable information, as well as testing within the IBA fleet, where the orientation of each device is synchronized for collective action.

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